

Constituents of *Rhamnus nipalensis*

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Abstract : Three flavonoids, 4,7-dimethoxyisoflavone, quercetin and kaempferol-4'-methyl ether have been isolated from the whole plant of *Rhamnus nipalensis* and their structures established by spectral evidences. This is the first report of these flavonoids in *R. nipalensis*.

Keywords : Flavonoids, *Rhamnus nipalensis*.

Rhamnus nipalensis Laws. (Rhamnaceae) is a shrub distributed throughout India and China and used in the treatment of herpes^{1,2}, and has been reported to possess hypotensive activity³. Rhamnetin, rhamnocitrin and their glycosides have earlier been reported from this plant⁴. Here we report the isolation of further three flavonoids from the whole plant of *R. nipalensis*.

Experimental

Air-dried whole plant (3.5 kg) of *Rhamnus nipalensis* was extracted with MeOH in a soxhlet extractor. The MeOH extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to a brown gummy mass (200 g) and the concentrate was chromatographed over silica gel column eluting with solvents of increasing polarity. The eluants collected from CHCl₃, CHCl₃-MeOH (20 : 1) and CHCl₃-MeOH (10 : 1) on crystallisation from MeOH furnished 4',7-dimethoxyisoflavone⁵ (1) (50 mg), m.p. 300–304 °C (dec.), kaempferol-4'-methylether⁶ (2) (22 mg), m.p. 227–229 °C and quercetin⁷ (3) (30 mg), m.p. 310–312 °C.

4',7-Dimethoxyisoflavone (1) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) 260, 290 (sh) and 330 (sh) nm; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) 1650 cm⁻¹ (chelated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.70 (s, Ar-OCH₃), 3.75 (s, Ar-OCH₃), 6.38 (m, H-6, H-8), 7.15–7.48 (m, H-5, H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5'), 7.82 (s, H-2); MS, *m/z* 282 (M⁺), 254, 134, 132 (Found : C, 72.4; H, 4.8. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₄O₄ : C, 72.3; H, 4.9%).

Kaempferol-4'-methyl ether (2) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) 254 (sh), 268, 299, 320 and 368 nm; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) 3200–3600 (br, OH), 1665 cm⁻¹ (chelated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.86 (s, Ar-

OCH₃), 6.34 (d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-6), 6.72 (d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-8), 6.93 (d, *J* 8.8 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 8.09 (d, *J* 8.8 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 9.51 (s, OH), 10.15 (s, OH), 12.47 (s, OH); MS, *m/z* 300 (M⁺), 272, 152, 148 (Found : C, 63.99; H, 4.01. Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₂O₆ : C, 64.00; H, 4.00%).

Quercetin (3) : It exhibited UV λ_{\max} (MeOH) 255, 265 (sh), 301 (sh) and 350 nm; IR ν_{\max} (KBr) 3200–3500 (br, OH), 1655 cm⁻¹ (chelated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 6.20 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-6), 6.38 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-8), 6.86 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3'), 7.22 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-6'), 7.27 (m, H-2'), 12.66 (br s, OH); MS, *m/z* 302 (M⁺), 274, 152, 151 (Found : C, 59.8; H, 3.03. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₀O₇ : C, 59.5 H, 3.04%).

The structures of all the above compounds were supported by a study of UV with shift reagents and direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR).

References

1. "The Wealth of India", Raw Materials. C.S.I.R., New Delhi, 1972, Vol. IX, p. 2.
2. K. R. Kirtikar and B. D. Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", eds. E. Blatter, J. F. Caisus and K. S. Mhaskar, 1975, Vol. I, p. 596.
3. M. L. Dhar, M. M. Dhar, B. N. Dhawan, B. N. Malhotra, R. C. Srimal and J. S. Tandon, *Indian J. Exptl. Biol.*, 1973, **11**, 51.
4. V. D. Tripathi, S. K. Agrawal and R. P. Rastogi, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, **17**, 89.
5. W. D. Ollis, *Experientia*, 1966, **22**, 777.
6. V. B. Pandey, S. P. D. Dwivedi, Y. V. Rao and R. K. Goel, *Fitoterapia*, 1990, **61**, 243.
7. Y. C. Tripathi, S. Devi, V. B. Pandey and A. H. Shah, *Fitoterapia*, 1988, **59**, 158.